

"The Conflict Between Acquisitive Prescription and Registered Rights in the Algerian Property System: A Legal Analysis"

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Abstract: *Since 1975, Algeria has adopted the Torrens system in order to purify land titles and achieve real estate security. However, this objective appears to remain elusive, given the Supreme Court's reluctance to issue a clear ruling on whether acquisitive prescription is permissible or prohibited with respect to properties that have registered (publicized) titles, This article aims to compile relevant decisions of the Supreme Court and to hypothetically identify their jurisprudential basis. Such analysis will allow us to better understand the legal reasoning underlying these rulings—whether in favor of or against acquisitive prescription, Ultimately, the article proposes a legal solution that we believe would help resolve the current evidentiary impasse in real estate matters, as this is the only means to achieve legal and judicial security for possessors as well as owners.*

Keywords: *Acquisitive Prescription, Land Titles, Property Dispute, Legal Certainty, Judicial Security, Plea of Unconstitutionality.*

I. Introduction

Real estate identity constitutes the foundation of property investment and relies on the existence of clear legal rules that are not subject to conflicting interpretations. However, anyone examining Algerian legislation in general, and real estate legislation in particular, will find it characterized by multiple sources: some provisions are rooted in religious principles, others in positive law; some are local in origin, while others have been imported. This reality cannot be overlooked. Its impact is evident in the sources of real property ownership. Acquisitive prescription represents a major legal institution in French law, which Algeria adopted in 1975¹, and it also finds support in Islamic jurisprudence. On the other hand, the land register (title deed) reflects the influence of the Australian

¹ *Order No: 75-58 in 28/09/1975, containing the Civil Code, Official Journal of the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria (hereinafter referred to as OJ), OJ No. 78 of 1975, as amended and supplemented.*

*Torrens system*². Due to legislative gaps and the desire to abolish French laws, these reforms were introduced without sufficient maturity, resulting in a conflict between these two concepts. This situation has given rise to a large body of contradictory judicial decisions governing the matter, without any definitive resolution being reached.

- **Research Question :**

What is the position of the Algerian Supreme Court regarding acquisitive prescription? Is it possible to formulate a legal approach that ensures both legal and judicial certainty for legal positions related to property ownership?

- **Objectives of the Research Paper :**

This article seeks to achieve several objectives, including an attempt to provide a doctrinal interpretation of the Supreme Court's decisions without favoring one opinion over another. Accordingly, the article aims to serve as a platform for constructive and balanced discussion between the competing concepts of acquisitive prescription and the land register system, in an effort to identify a solution to the partial crisis of real estate proof in Algeria. It also seeks to classify the decisions of the Algerian Supreme Court and analyze their approach to real property ownership.

- **Structure of the Paper :**

To achieve these objectives, the paper is divided into three parts. The first part examines the Supreme Court decisions that recognize acquisitive prescription. The second part discusses the decisions that reject its application. The third part presents a concept that this article seeks to establish and further develop when the opportunity arises: the notion of legislative responsibility and the constitutional challenge to Article 827 of the Algerian Civil Code.

II. First/ Supreme Court Jurisprudence in Support of Acquisitive Prescription :

This section aims to identify and analyze the Supreme Court decisions that support the application of acquisitive prescription, based on prevailing legal and jurisprudential principles, as follows:

² Algeria adopted this system pursuant to Order No: 75-74 in 18/11/1975, concerning the preparation of the general land survey and the establishment of the land registry, OJ No: 92 of 1975, as amended and supplemented.

A* Identification of the Decisions:

- **The first decision states:**

"The jurisprudence of the Supreme Court has been consistent in affirming that acquisitive prescription applies against all rights holders, regardless of the nature of their titles. There is no provision in the law that prohibits prescription, especially since determining whether acquisitive prescription applies (as opposed to pleading or invoking it) is a matter of public order"³.

- **The second decision affirms:**

"The Civil Code does not distinguish, in matters of acquisitive prescription, between property with registered titles and that without. This principle is also confirmed by Decree No. 83/253 concerning the procedures for proving acquisitive prescription and preparing the notoriety deed recognizing ownership, which stipulates that all land is subject to prescription. Accordingly, the appellants' claim that land with registered titles is not subject to acquisitive prescription is unfounded"⁴.

- **The third decision states:**

"There is no legal provision that prohibits invoking acquisitive prescription under Article 827 of the Civil Code, even if a land title exists in the form of a land register"⁵.

- **The fourth decision provides:**

"It is well established under Article 827 of the Civil Code that one who possesses a property, even without being its legal owner, acquires ownership if the possession continues uninterrupted for 15 years. This indicates that possession is a valid legal means of acquiring ownership—even against a holder of a valid title—since the article does not exclude properties with registered contracts"⁶.

- **The fifth decision asserts:**

³ The Supreme Court of Algeria, Real Estate Chamber, Case No. 0798374, Decision dated 12/12/2013, Supreme Court Journal, No. 02, 2013, pp. 333–336 (The Supreme Court of Algeria will be referred to in short SCA, Real Estate Chamber will be referred to in short REC, Supreme Court Journal will be referred to in short SCJ)

⁴ SCA, REC, Case No: 300815, 18/05/2005, SCJ, Special Issue, Part III, 2010, pp. 268–273.

⁵ SCA, REC, Case No: 423832, 16/07/2008, SCJ, Special Issue, Part III, 2010, pp. 274–279.

⁶ SCA, REC, Case No: 479371, 15/10/2008, SCJ, No: 2, 2008, pp. 273–275.

"A person who possesses a parcel of land for 15 years becomes its owner by virtue of acquisitive prescription, which carries absolute authority against all parties."⁷

B. Analysis of the Decisions:

Thus, an examination of these decisions allows us to establish a set of arguments justifying the preference for acquisitive prescription over the land registry, namely:

01. The Criterion of Textuality:

This can be divided into a temporal textuality, which holds that the applicable law remains in force, and that acquisitive prescription is a living concept under Article 1 of the Algerian Civil Code, which stipulates: "The law shall apply to all matters addressed in its texts, whether explicitly or implicitly"⁸, the establishment of its applicability is a matter of public order, which necessitates its enforcement, as its exclusion would undermine the principle of separation of powers and constitute an abuse of authority. A judge cannot exercise discretion where a clear legal provision exists. Moreover, the repeal of a law requires an explicit or implicit provision, according to Article 2 of the same Code, which is absent in this case, accordingly, the Supreme Court held in one of its rulings: "to demonstrate the corruption of the approach adopted by some of its judges by requiring an official title negating ambiguity to prove ownership, under the pretext that this is the orientation of modern real estate legislation"⁹.

It is important to highlight here the Egyptian experience, as it represents the historical background of the Algerian Civil Code. The Egyptian Constitutional Court issued a ruling¹⁰ explicitly rejecting any infringement upon the rules of acquisitive prescription, considering such an act a violation of the constitutional protection guaranteed for property rights. Furthermore, the ruling emphasized that it breaches the principle of equality by unjustifiably distinguishing between legitimate and illegitimate grounds for ownership, The Court also refuted the erroneous notion that the Real Estate Registry Law of 1964 repealed the relevant provisions of the Civil Code of 1958 concerning acquisitive possession leading to ownership. This is due to the difference in subject matter governed by each law: while the Civil Code addresses real rights (their creation, transfer, and elements), the Real Estate Registry Law solely deals with the proof of such rights, thus leaving acquisitive prescription intact and preserving all its legal effects.

The second type pertains to linguistic textuality, which must be activated when applying interpretative rules to Article 827 of the Civil Code. According to established interpretive principles, a general provision must be applied in its generality, and no exceptions may be introduced unless explicitly stated by the law. The article, in its literal wording, states: "Whoever possesses a movable or immovable property, or a real right whether movable or

⁷ SCA, REC, Case No: 1185565, 15/12/2016, SCJ, No:2, 2016.

⁸ SCA, REC, Case No:0798374, 12/12/2013, SCJ, No:02, 2013, p. 333.

⁹ SCA, REC, Case No:0835419, 13/03/2014, SCJ, No:01, 2014, pp. 360–363.

¹⁰ Constitutional Ruling No: 42 of Judicial Year 17, dated 06/06/1998.

immovable, without being its owner or having a special title to it, shall acquire ownership if possession continues uninterrupted for fifteen (15) years." This text is clearly general, with no exceptions mentioned. This interpretation is affirmed in the five Supreme Court decisions referenced above. It also finds application in French jurisprudence, where courts recognize possession that contradicts urban planning schemes, since Article 2272 of the French Civil Code contains no exceptions either¹¹.

In continuation of this approach, interpretation requires adherence to the most coherent¹² and comprehensive meaning within the context of the legal system as a whole¹³, rather than within the scope of a single law. This is because the body of laws collectively expresses a legislative vision of the matters it governs—what may be referred to as compositional structuralism—which in turn enables us to uncover the legislative purpose behind legal provisions in general, and real estate laws in particular—a purpose grounded in operational structuralism, namely, the regularization of property ownership, a goal in which acquisitive prescription plays a significant role, as it functions to convert a de facto situation into a legal one, assigning the right to the person who has effectively manifested the outward signs of ownership over a prolonged period¹⁴. More precisely, acquisitive prescription serves as a foundational mechanism for harmonizing a factual situation with a legal status, making its preservation essential for the realization of this objective.

02/ The Self-Sufficiency of Acquisitive Prescription :

This criterion is inspired by the concept of negotiable instruments, which are self-contained documents independent of any underlying banking obligation. The same applies to acquisitive prescription, which is independent of any formal title. This independence stems from its dual functionality: on one hand, it is a legal mode of acquiring ownership, as provided under Articles 808–843 of the Algerian Civil Code¹⁵; on the other hand, it operates as a means of proof. Once acquisitive prescription is established, ownership is deemed proven—based on a set of evidentiary elements, particularly the widespread recognition of the possessor as the owner of the property, which reflects a form of de facto publicity. This self-sufficiency is also

¹¹ French Court of Cassation, 3e Civ., 21 septembre 2022, n° 21-17.409, (B), FS, <https://www.courdecassation.fr/publications/bulletin-des-arrets-des-chambres-civiles/numero-9-septembre-2022/prescription-acquisitive>

¹² Russell C. Bogue, *Statutory Structure*, 132/5 Yale L.J. 1532 (2023).

¹³ The Algerian Constitutional Court stated: "The interpretation of a constitutional provision must not occur in isolation from other related provisions of the Constitution. Given the Constitution's supremacy, it forms an indivisible and coherent system. Therefore, its provisions must not be interpreted outside the framework of the objectives and purposes for which they were enacted, nor should they be read in a manner detached from their true meaning or contextual setting." See: Algerian Constitutional Court, Opinion No: 01, 07/08/2023, concerning the interpretation of Article 127 of the Constitution, OJ, No: 59 of 2023.

¹⁴ Ambroise Colin & Henri Capitant, *Cours élémentaire de droit civil français vol. 1*, 878–79 (6th ed. 1930).

¹⁵ This corresponds to the following provisions in comparative legal systems: Articles 949–984 of the Egyptian Civil Code, Articles 2255–2278 of the French Civil Code, Articles 239–264 of the Moroccan Law on Real Rights, Articles 921–933 and 2910–2920 of the Civil Code of Quebec (Canada), Articles 916–937, 724, and 728 of the Swiss Civil Code, and Articles 430–466 and 1940–1960 of the Spanish Civil Code.

evident in the fact that a person invoking acquisitive prescription is not required to present a title deed¹⁶. Accordingly, acquisitive prescription embodies a rational principle that confers legal status upon long-term possession by providing the possessor with a form of title that justifies and reinforces their legal standing.

In fact, acquisitive prescription is not only applied in the absence of title deeds but is also enforced even when such deeds exist. It embodies the protection of acquired rights without distinction between the reasons for possession (inheritance, contract, registration, etc.)¹⁷. This principle is also applied in Tunisian jurisprudence, which holds that “possession is a conclusive presumption of ownership of immovable or movable property and alone is sufficient to acquire ownership of the property if its conditions are met.”¹⁸ Furthermore, one of its rulings states: “Possession is an established proof and an independent cause of ownership that stands by itself without needing to explain its source.”¹⁹ Similarly, the Egyptian Court of Cassation has ruled: “It is established in its jurisprudence that the claimant of ownership may base his claim on any reason he deems sufficient. Acquiring ownership by long prescription constitutes an independent cause of ownership, which legitimizes the possession by itself and therefore negates the status of usurpation.”²⁰

To further support this criterion, it is worth invoking the opinion of jurist Oliver Wendell Holmes Jr., in a decision of the Supreme Judicial Court of Massachusetts, where he described acquisitive prescription as: “It destroys another’s legal position without any notice or judicial proceeding whatsoever”²¹, This is because the realization of prescription does not rely on any external procedural mechanism. Holmes justified this conclusion by acknowledging that, although the result may disappoint the expectations of the former owner, such disappointment is warranted by the owner's negligence, which allowed for a progressive detachment from the

¹⁶ his issue is addressed within the Maliki school of Islamic jurisprudence, one of the major schools of Islamic law. See, for example: *Abi al-Hasan Ali Abd al-Salam al-Tasuli, Al-Bahjah fi Sharh al-Tuhfah (in Arabic), Vol. 2, 1st Edition, Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyyah, Lebanon, 1998, pp. 315–316*. Also see Article 242 of the Moroccan Code of Real Rights, as Moroccan law is derived from the Maliki school of jurisprudence, which is explicitly stated in Article 1 of the same code and Henri Capitant, *Introduction à l'étude du droit civil: Notions générales* 372 (5th ed. 1929) and G. Baudry-Lacantinerie, *Précis de droit civil: Conforme au programme des Facultés de droit, Tome I*, 801 (Librairie du Recueil Sirey 1941).

¹⁷ Marie-Louis Beaulieu, *Analyse de la possession*, 4 Les Cahiers de Droit 5, 5–15 (1961).

¹⁸ Tunisian Court of Cassation, *Decision No. 24567, dated 23/02/2016* (Tunisian Court of Cassation will be referred to in short TCC)

¹⁹ TCC, (Civil Chamber), *Decision No: 7534, 09/02/1971; Decision No: 33701, 22/11/1994; Decision No: 33686, 15/02/1994; Decision No: 1740, 26/02/1980; Decision No: 1245, 10/04/1979; Decision No: 1495, 07/07/1977; Decision No: 8161, 12/10/1971.*

²⁰ The Egyptian Court of Cassation has held that: “It is established in its jurisprudence that a claimant of ownership may base their claim on any cause they consider sufficient to confer ownership. Acquisition of ownership by long-term prescription constitutes an independent ground for ownership, , *Decision No. 4929 of Judicial Year 85, session dated 20 June 2021*).

²¹ *Massachusetts Supreme Judicial Court tyler v. Judges of Court of Registration, 175 Mass. 71 (1900)*, see: <https://cite.case.law/mass/175/71/>, 30/06/2022.

property in question, and a gradual attachment to the possessor, Furthermore, the former owner is presumed to know in advance the legal consequences of prescription rules—namely, that ownership will be transferred to the possessor once the conditions of possession are met.²² Therefore, it is the owner's responsibility to interrupt the prescriptive period by any legal means, rather than demand the suspension or non-application of such rules, From this perspective, it becomes increasingly difficult to justify withdrawing ownership from the current possessor—who has acquired it lawfully through prescription—in favor of a previous owner who abandoned it. Rational legal reasoning favors the one in possession over the one who neglected.

3. The Economic Criterion :

Security has become one of the most debated topics in Algeria, with many facets. Here, we shall focus on two of its principal branches: legal security and economic security.

In terms of legal security, a compelling argument emerges, especially considering that the legislator enshrined it constitutionally through Article 34/4 of the 2020 constitutional amendment²³, which states: "To achieve legal security, the State shall ensure, when enacting legislation related to rights and freedoms, that such legislation is accessible, clear, and stable", these are fundamental principles that reflect the need to protect legal positions. Article 827 of the Algerian Civil Code, which governs acquisitive prescription, is clear and provides an implicit promise of ownership²⁴ once the three elements of possession (material, intentional, and temporal) are satisfied. This reflects a preference for dynamic legal security over static legal security, and thereby justifies granting ownership to the individual who actively uses the land — and thereby contributes to the economy — rather than to the (dormant) titleholder who exercises mere formal ownership, ignoring the social function of property; furthermore, this article has remained unchanged and stable since its introduction in 1975, despite amendments to the Civil Code in 1988, 2005, and 2007. If the legislator had intended to abolish acquisitive prescription, it could have done so — but it did not, therefore, the legislative intent must be respected and should not be altered arbitrarily.

At the level of economic security, a partial reflection of this concept can be found in the Constitution; because Article 21 imposes an obligation on the State to protect agricultural lands. In application of this principle, Article 48 of the Land Orientation Law²⁵ enshrines the notion that failing to cultivate agricultural land constitutes an abuse of property rights, in view

²² *The law can ask no better justification than the deepest instincts of man. It is only by way of reply to the suggestion that you are disappointing the former owner, , that you refer to his neglect having allowed the gradual dissociation between himself and what he claims, and the gradual association of it with another, Oliver Wendel (HOLMES), The Path of the Law, pp 37,38.*

²³ *Presidential Decree No: 20-442 in 30/12/2020, concerning the promulgation of the constitutional amendment approved by the referendum of 1 November 2020, published in the Official journal of the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria, JO No: 82 of 2020.*

²⁴ *Article 930 of the Civil Code of Quebec states that "Possession vests the possessor with the real right he is exercising if he complies with the rules on prescription."*

²⁵ *Law No: 90-25 in 18/11/1990, on Land Orientation, OJ, No: 49 of 1992, as amended and supplemented.*

of the economic importance and social function of such lands, this legal provision establishes a duty upon both owners and possessors to actively invest in and utilize agricultural properties. It defines non-invested land as any agricultural parcel that remains uncultivated for at least two consecutive farming seasons. A regulatory body is tasked with verifying non-utilization, and if proven, the following measures may be imposed:

- ❖ *Placing the land under cultivation at the expense of the owner or apparent possessor, if the actual owner is unknown.*
- ❖ *Offering the land for lease.*
- ❖ *Selling the land, if it is classified as fertile or highly fertile.*

The provisions relating to acquisitive prescription and abuse of rights are inherently interconnected. Abuse of rights is generally established in three situations²⁶, the most relevant to our discussion being the second: when the benefit derived by the right-holder is minimal compared to the harm caused to others, applied to agricultural lands, the failure to cultivate such land serves merely as an expression of ownership sovereignty — a negligible benefit when weighed against the resulting harm. First, the land itself deteriorates into barrenness, and second, restoring it to productive condition incurs significant costs. This reality stands in contradiction with constitutional principles that promote the establishment of a productive and competitive economy, within a framework of sustainable development and preservation of natural resources — including agricultural land — for future generations. Third, such neglect poses a threat to food security, which is recognized as a strategic objective of the nation.

4. Absence of the Exclusive Possession:

The concept of exclusive possession²⁷ refers to the idea that only the rightful owner—whether directly or indirectly—has the sole authority to exercise possession, under this theory, any other possessor must justify their possession, with preference given to the titleholder in accordance with the principle of legitimate possession, however, this concept is not adopted under Algerian law. In fact, the legislator provides greater protection to the possessor than to the owner, and refuses to adjudicate ownership claims until possession-related disputes are resolved and the corresponding rulings are executed, this legal framework clearly prioritizes possession as an independent legal status²⁸, further evidence of the legislator's rejection of this exclusivity notion lies in the significant legal attention given to possession: 36 substantive articles and 7 procedural articles are dedicated to its protection. It would be illogical for the

²⁶ Article 124 bis of the Algerian Civil Code provides:

“The abusive exercise of a right constitutes a fault, particularly in the following cases:

- If it is carried out with the intent to harm others;*
- If it aims to obtain a negligible benefit compared to the harm caused to others;*
- If its purpose is to achieve an unlawful benefit”.*

²⁷ *The process of analyzing judicial decisions allows us to identify certain key terms and concepts, even if these terms were used in different contexts originally, this does not prevent us from adapting and applying them in new contexts to support our arguments in this article, one such term was found in a decision by the High Court of Australia: High Court of Australia, Wik peoples v Queensland, <https://eresources.hcourt.gov.au/showbyHandle/1/11830>.*

²⁸ *Article 530 of Law No. 08-09 in 25/02/2008, concerning the Code of Civil and Administrative Procedures, OJ No: 21 of 2008, as amended and supplemented.*

legislator to emphasize possession to such an extent while disregarding its legal consequences, moreover, Algerian law prohibits the consolidation of possession and ownership claims, and prevents the possessor from justifying their possession by invoking ownership deeds, affirming once again the independence of possession from ownership²⁹, This approach is consistently upheld by Algerian courts³⁰.

The idea of exclusive possession is applied in the Tunisian real estate system, where registration systems operate peacefully and within precise limits, through the adoption of two procedural mechanisms: the possession lawsuit for unregistered properties³¹, where possession must be continuous for more than one year and the possessor must appear as the owner, aiming to stabilize apparent situations in unregistered properties; and the "Action to Stop Interference with Possession"³² lawsuit, which aims to protect the owner of registered properties³³ from any physical act or legal transaction, directly or indirectly, intended to prevent him from exploiting his property. A possessor cannot claim possession over a registered property because, no matter how long possession lasts, it cannot lead to ownership³⁴. This idea is logical because Tunisia allows those harmed by registration to file a compensation claim, which does not exist in Algeria. Therefore, the idea is logical in Tunisia but illogical in Algeria.

05/The Selective Application of the Torrens System in Algeria :

Anyone who closely examines the essence of the Torrens system will find that the Algerian legislator did not adopt it as a complete and integrated institution³⁵, but rather in a fragmented

²⁹ It is necessary here to point out two important issues. First, the jurisprudence of Imam Malik—one of the major schools of Islamic jurisprudence—explicitly states, when discussing the hierarchy of evidentiary proofs, a preference for ownership over possession.

Second, the principle of prohibiting the joining of claims for ownership and possession is, in the opinion of the author of this article, a rejected principle due to the defects inherent in it. This matter will be the subject of a future article, God willing, as well as a constitutional challenge petition.

³⁰ The Algerian Supreme Court stated: "In possession leading to acquisition by acquisitive prescription, proof is not limited to official contracts but can be established by all means of evidence. Accordingly, the preference by the judges of the Judicial Council (Court of Appeal) for the possession held by the respondent, established according to the law, over the official contracts relied upon by the other parties, is a correct application of the law", Real Estate Chamber, Case No.: 232683, Decision dated: 22/05/2002, Supreme Court Journal, Issue No. 01, 2003, pp. 326-330.

³¹ TCC, (Civil Chamber), Decisions No:38891 19/04/2017; No:29266 07/03/2016; No:51115 19/04/2018; No:58008 16/04/2018; and No:60281 23/04/2019.

³² Action en cessation de trouble de possession in French.

³³ TCC, (Civil Chamber), Decisions No: 24182 17/08/2020; No: 31411 06/10/2021; No: 38728 12/04/2017.

³⁴ The Tunisian Court of Cassation clarified the distinction between the two actions in Decision No. 67496 dated 19/12/2018.

³⁵ We may borrow the metaphors used by one researcher to describe the Canadian land tenure system: we are faced with a legal anomaly—an abnormal situation within the legal framework—based on the coexistence of different systems under a selective approach that contributes to the complexity of the land law regime. It is a system of hybridization; a form of legal schizophrenia. See: Gaële Gidrol-Mistral & Thuy Nam Tran Tran, *Publicité des droits et prescription acquisitive : des liaisons dangereuses?*, 46 Rev. gén. dr. 303, 307 (2016).

and distorted manner³⁶. This is evident, for example, in the limited evidentiary value of the land title, unlike in other countries. In Australia, for instance, the title deed is given absolute evidentiary authority³⁷ and is protected from any form of acquisition outside of this system. The core of the Torrens system lies in making the title deed conclusive evidence of its contents, thereby protecting the registered owner against any legal action aiming to recover the land³⁸. This ensures that the registered owner holds the land entirely free of any other interests (rights), a principle that is firmly upheld in court rulings. Thus, the function of registration is not merely to provide a historical record of ownership at a given time; it serves as a tool to establish an independent, final, and irrevocable title of ownership—regardless of any cause for annulment³⁹, this is not the case in Algeria, where property rights remain subject to continuous review. Therefore, it is misleading to describe the system with attributes or ideals that have not been legally established by the Algerian legislator.

³⁶ The implementation of the Torrens system was the subject of a critical study we conducted in a research paper titled "The Effectiveness of the Real Property Registration System in Achieving Land Title Purification in Algeria: A Study on the Impact of Ordinance 75-74 Establishing the General Survey and the Land Registry", presented at the conference held at the University of Boumerdes under the theme "Land Security in Arab Countries: Between the Necessity of Implementation and the Challenges of Application", on 19/11/2023. After examining the roots of this system in Algeria from 1886 to the present day, we identified two key criteria to distinguish between the genuine Torrens system and the Algerian version: **uniformity** and **justice**. Algeria lacks a compensation fund, which is a core component of the original Torrens model. This issue was the subject of a second research paper entitled "Preliminary Ideas for the Establishment of a Real Estate Assurance Fund in Algeria", presented at the conference on "Land Title Purification in Arab Legislation", also held at the University of Boumerdes (Algeria) on 27/11/2023.

³⁷ sections 68 and 134 give expression to, and at the same time qualify, the principle of indefeasibility of title which is the foundation of the Torrens system of title. High Court of Australia, *Bahr v Nicolay (no 02)*, 1988 HCA, 16, <https://eresources.hcourt.gov.au/showbyHandle/1/11768>, Paragraph 10.

³⁸ except

- (a) "in the case of fraud"—which means except in the case that the registration as proprietor was obtained by the proprietor's own fraud—see *Assets Co. Ltd. v. Mere Roihi* ;
- (b) in the case of a proprietor claiming the same land under a prior certificate of title or under a certificate of title issued under Pt III of the amendment of the Act in 1952, i.e. a certificate based on a possessory title, or under a prior registered grant;
- (c) in the case of right of way or other easement omitted from or misdescribed in the certificate of title; and
- (d) in the case of the wrong description of the land or of its boundaries.

See : *Breskvar v. Wall*, (1971) HCA 70 (Austl.), <https://eresources.hcourt.gov.au/showbyHandle/1/11167>.

³⁹ *Latec Invs. Ltd. v. Hotel Terrigal Pty Ltd*, (1965) HCA 17 (Austl.), ¶¶ 9–10, <https://eresources.hcourt.gov.au/showbyHandle/1/10804>.

06/ The Hypothetical Criterion:

This refers to a set of assumptions that can be used to support the application of acquisitive prescription, these assumptions include:

06/01 : The Owner as a Representative of the Nation in Land Use:

*This assumption requires a shift from the classical notion⁴⁰ that the owner represents only themselves, toward a more rational perspective that sees the owner as merely a representative of the nation in the use of land. If the owner fails in this role, they must be removed—either through **Article 48 of the Land Orientation Law**, which constitutes a legal form of removal, or through **Article 827 of the Civil Code**, which allows for de facto removal. In such cases, a more suitable representative—the possessor—should be appointed and their position strengthened by transferring ownership to them.*

06/02 : The Concept of Sanction⁴¹:

Acquisitive prescription can be viewed as a sanction for the prolonged non-use (or neglect) of ownership. The rationale behind recognizing acquisitive prescription is the stabilization of apparent legal situations⁴², an old court decision supported this view, stating “: the date of purchase, which dates back to 1846, and the fact that the plaintiff did not actively use the property until 1868, results in a 22-year inactivity that is difficult to comprehend and appears to reflect their lack of confidence in their position”⁴³, this implicitly means that when strong evidence supports the possessor’s claim leading to prescription, it becomes a legal outcome worthy of full protection⁴⁴, this reasoning is further supported by a Tunisian court ruling, which held: “evidence of ownership loses its effect in the presence of possession that meets all legal conditions. Although title deeds preserve the right of the holder, the expiration

⁴⁰ Among the modern definitions of ownership is the one formulated by Wesley Newcomb Hohfeld, who defined it as “a set of legal relationships between persons.” This definition aligns with our earlier argument, as it transforms ownership into a four-party relationship: between the owner, the possessor, the authorities (both administrative and judicial), and the nation. Ownership, then, is perceived as a value or interest, and preference should be given to the party capable of investing in the property. This idea aligns with the philosophy of jurist **Roscoe Pound**, where ownership is weighed based on the capacity to fulfill its social and economic purpose, for further reading, see: Kenneth J. Vandeveld et al., *The New Property in the Nineteenth Century: The Development of the Modern Concept of Property*, 29 *Buff. L. Rev.* 330 (1980) and Roscoe Pound, *A Survey of Social Interests*, 57 *Harv. L. Rev.* 1 (1943).

⁴¹ It is well established in the philosophy of law that sanction is a fundamental component of the legal rule in the formalist school of thought (Kelsen, Ihering, Savigny, Hegel, Austin). In line with this approach, we adopt the assumption that acquisitive prescription functions as a sanction and a limitation on the failure to utilize ownership over a prolonged period—durations that vary depending on the legal context (5, 10, 20, 30, or 33 years).

⁴² Court of Cassation [Bahrain], Appeal No. 829 of 2022, June 5, 2022.

⁴³ la Cour impériale d'Alger 1^{er} Ch. — (24 janv. 1870), *Ben Haisi frères c. le préfet d'Oran*, *JJCI (CPA)*, n: 11, 1870, pp 19-23.

⁴⁴ la Cour impériale d'Alger 1^{er} Ch. — (19 décembre 1877), *Lambert c. commune de Blida*, *JJCI (CPA)*, n: 20, 1878.

of the legal period during which a person abandons use of unregistered land—while another uses it without opposition—strips the titleholder of legal protection and is considered a de facto renunciation in favor of the possessor"⁴⁵.

06/03: The Concept of a Promise of a Reward:

*This concept is analogous to the idea of a promise of a reward as stipulated in **Article 123 bis 01 of the Algerian Civil Code**: "anyone who promises the public a reward for performing a certain act is bound to give it to the person who performs that act" in this analogy:*

- ❖ **The promisor:** *The legislator, theoretically, and the judiciary, practically.*
- ❖ **The promisee:** *The possessor.*
- ❖ **The act:** *Possession fulfilling all its requirements.*
- ❖ **The reward:** *Acquisition of property ownership (acquisitive prescription).*

6/4: Prescription as an Implied Transfer⁴⁶ of Ownership:

In general, legal acts are governed by the principle of the autonomy of will. Therefore, acquisitive prescription serves a dual purpose: on the one hand, it indicates the owner's implicit renunciation of their property, consistent with their freedom to dispose of it. This inference is supported by Article 537 of the French Civil Code⁴⁷, and confirmed by French jurisprudence, on the other hand, it reflects the intention of the potential owner (the possessor) to become the actual owner. Interpretation of legal behavior is generally based on outward, observable acts rather than internal intentions, a close examination of the evolution of possession rights reveals that the legislator requires legal action to recover possession within one year of its loss. Some legal scholars⁴⁸ justify this short timeframe based on a legal presumption that anyone who fails to take material or legal steps to reclaim possession within a year implicitly expresses a willingness to relinquish it.

We adopt and expand this idea to the domain of acquisitive prescription: a person who does not act for 15 consecutive years to recover their right either: was never the true owner, or has implicitly and gratuitously renounced possession, thus, acquisitive prescription can be seen as a presumed gift, contingent upon the possessor having served the property for 15 full year or, if you prefer, it is a presumed sale, where the price is time⁴⁹, this transformation of rights

⁴⁵ TCC, Civil Cassation Decision No: 62687, 02/02/1999.

⁴⁶ *he concept of transformation of legal rights is recognized in Algerian law, notably in Article 105 of the Civil Code, which states: "If a contract is void or voidable, but it contains the elements of another valid contract, it shall be considered valid as the contract whose elements are fulfilled, provided that the intention of the contracting parties was directed toward concluding that contract."*

⁴⁷ *Say "Individuals have the free disposal of the property they own, subject to the modifications established by law."*

⁴⁸ C. Aubry & C. Rau, *Cours de droit civil français: d'après l'ouvrage allemand de C.-S. Zachariae*, vol. 2, Imprimerie et Librairie Générale de Jurisprudence 1863, at 75, merge 15.

⁴⁹ *In Algerian family law (which is derived from Islamic Sharia), a husband's abandonment of his wife in the marital bed for four months, or his failure to provide for her financially for one year, constitutes a legitimate ground for divorce, similarly, in property law, abandonment of a property and failure to*

reflects the evolution of active rights and serves as a penalty for dormant ones, thereby ensuring the activation of property's social function⁵⁰.

07/ The Criterion of Jealousy:

Land holds a special place among Algerians; it is like their women, a symbol of honor. This is why the saying goes: "Land is honor." The French noticed this during their occupation of Algeria. An old ruling by the Imperial Court stated: "It is established that there is no right more zealously guarded by the indigenous inhabitants (i.e., Algerians) than the right of ownership"⁵¹, to such an extent, there is a particular type of property called "Bilad al-Baroud" (Land of Gunpowder⁵²), over which people fight fiercely to possess. This passion for land caused them to sacrifice more than 1,500,000 people in resisting French colonialism during the War of Independence from November 1954 to July 1962, ultimately gaining their independence.

Currently, disputes over land before the courts often occur even within the same family or between neighbors, sometimes escalating to killing over boundary issues. For this reason, it is extremely rare for someone to abandon their land due to this deep zeal, this leads us to say that acquisitive prescription likely has some hidden source or justification⁵³ (such as a customary or oral contract) because an Algerian does not simply abandon his land.

III. Supreme Court Decisions Rejecting Acquisitive Prescription:

We will identify these decisions and then analyze them according to relevant legal theories and principles, as follows:

A. Identification of the Decisions:

• The first Decision:

The Administrative Chamber ruled: "the procedures prescribed in the decree related to the contract of 'shahra' (registration contract), based on possession as defined in Articles 827 and 828 of the Civil Code, are excluded from application whenever there exists an official and registered title deed for the property, as is the case here. This confirms that the property

maintain or invest in it for more than 15 full years also justifies acquisitive prescription, as a means to protect the dignity of the property.

⁵⁰ Francis Roy, *Du certificat de localisation et de la reconnaissance des droits acquis en matière d'urbanisme: la portée de l'opinion professionnelle de l'arpenteur-géomètre*, *Revue du notariat*, vol. 108, no. 2, 2006, pp. 225–271.

⁵¹ "Qu'il est constant qu'il n'y a pas de droit dont les indigènes se montrent plus jaloux que du droit de propriété", *la Cour impériale d'Alger 1^{er} Ch.* (19 juin 1877), *Rekik et cons. c. commune d'Ain-Sultan*, *JJCI (CPA)*, n° 19, 1877. Pp 201-206.

⁵² *Court of appeal of Algiers (01 che)*, March 18, 1878, *The Oulad-Amranes C. the Oulad-Ziad and The State*, *Judicial Bulletin of Algeria: doctrine, jurisprudence, legislation*, No. 48, 16/ 12/1878, pp: 387-396.

⁵³ For this reason, the Egyptian Court of Cassation holds that possession constitutes a conclusive legal presumption of the existence of a valid cause for ownership, case No. 2174 of Judicial Year 84, dated 25/02/2021.

*registrar's refusal to register a 'shahra' contract on a previously registered property is a legally sound and justified action, relying on the purpose of Decree 33/352, which aims to clear the real estate situation of properties that have not undergone the general survey"*⁵⁴.

• ***The second Decision:***

"The plea of possession leading to acquisitive prescription is not admissible after the exhaustion of procedures and deadlines established for objections to provisional numbering and issuance of the land registry, which constitutes the ownership title, since accepting it would conflict with the principle of absolute probative force of the land registry."⁵⁵

• ***The third Decision:***

"It is legally established that the land registry is the sole evidence to prove real estate ownership"⁵⁶.

• ***The fourth Decision:***

"It is legally settled that real estate ownership is only proven by official documents consisting of notarized contracts and administrative contracts registered with the land registry"⁵⁷.

B/ Analysis of the Decisions:

01/ Procedural Economy:

Those who defend the absolute probative force of the land registry against acquisitive prescription may justify this by procedural economy, it relieves contracting parties from having to investigate the chain of ownership⁵⁸; this registry alone serves as the definitive source of real estate truth, moreover, it is characterized by simplicity, especially with the digitization of survey documents on the "Espace Algérie" platform⁵⁹, which enables digital verification. This contrasts with acquisitive prescription, where it is often difficult to verify the true owner because possession is usually a factual situation lacking concrete (documentary) evidence to justify it, which may lead to many disputes.

One can respond to this argument by saying that procedural economy actually works against the registered owner more than the possessor. The reason is that the owner failed to appreciate the efforts of the Survey and Real Estate Registration Administration (land registry

⁵⁴ SCA, Administrative Chamber, Decision No: 146, dated March 9, 1998, published in the State Property Texts Collection for the year 1999, pages 23-26.

⁵⁵ SCA, Decision No: 1206937, 14/01/2021, available at: <https://cutt.us/R7he6>, accessed on: 11/05/2024.

⁵⁶ SCA, Civil Chamber, Decision No: 197920, 28/06/2000, published in the Judicial Review, Issue No. 01, 2001, pages 249-253.

⁵⁷ Council of State, Decision No. 024778, dated 28/06/2006.

⁵⁸ *It came in an Australian court decision: the object is to save persons dealing with registered proprietors from the trouble and expense of going behind the register, in order to investigate the history of their author's title, and to satisfy themselves of its validity. HCA, Bahr v Nicolay [No 2], 1988, April 15, <https://eresources.hcourt.gov.au/showbyHandle/1/11768>.*

⁵⁹ <https://fadaeldjazair.mf.gov.dz/ar/>

in other countries), as well as the huge funds spent on property regularization. Simply put, the owner neglected their property and did not invest in it. Therefore, they deserve to be treated accordingly, with preference given to the possessor based on the principle of “let him work, let him pass; let him possess, let him own”.

Moreover, acquisitive prescription represents a renewal of the land registry by replacing an inactive owner with an active one⁶⁰. This renewal is a strategic goal aimed at making the land registry the authoritative and reliable official record. As a general rule, the land registry book is required for registration procedures, except in exceptional cases such as: the existence of a judicial decision issued without the owner's assistance or against them, and acquisitive prescription falls under both cases because it seeks to legally deprive the owner of their property without their assistance, thus, this is nothing but an application of Article 50 of Decree No. 76-63⁶¹.

This argument has also been implicitly addressed by the French Court of Cassation, which has allowed acquisitive prescription to be enforced even against registered ownership⁶², the rationale is that it embodies legal certainty by giving settled factual situations a legal character—thus unifying legal and factual reality⁶³, this is a logical response, as one cannot, under the pretext of alleged procedural economy, disregard real estate ownership, which represents a legacy for both current and future generations, as previously noted.

2. Unification of Rules of Evidence :

Some argue that the land registry book (title deed) should be the sole proof of ownership. It is also worth noting that legal instability hinders legal certainty and trust, especially since the proliferation of laws creates confusion, fueled by continuous conflict between overlapping legal frameworks. Legal uncertainty is a natural consequence of contradictory interpretations related to property rights⁶⁴, and the multiplicity of evidentiary sources is merely a reflection of this legal disorder, the implicit justification often used to support the adoption of the title deed as the sole basis for proof is that it resolves the evidentiary crisis by unifying the means of proof within the realm of real property ownership on the one hand, and by establishing a hierarchical system for evidentiary rules on the other.

⁶⁰ *It came in an Australian court decision: the ordinary operation of the Act 42 (it's mean Real Property Act 1900) is to produce and preserve correspondence between legal entitlement and the state of the register, HCA, Corin v Patton, 1990, April 9, <https://eresources.hcourt.gov.au/showbyHandle/1/9201>*

⁶¹ *Decree No. 76-63 of March 25, 1976, concerning the establishment of the land register, OJ No. 30 of 1976.*

⁶² *French Court of Cassation, 3e Civ., 17 décembre 2020, n° 18-24.434, (P), <https://www.courdecassation.fr/publications/bulletin-des-arrets-des-chambres-civiles/numero-12-decembre-2020/prescription-acquisitive>*

⁶³ *cour de cassation francaise, 3e Civ., 4 janvier 2023, n° 21-18.993, (B), FS, <https://www.courdecassation.fr/publications/bulletin-des-arrets-des-chambres-civiles/numero-1-janvier-2023/prescription-acquisitive> .*

⁶⁴ *la Cour impériale d'Alger 1^{er} Ch, (19 juin 1877), REKIK ET CONS. C. COMMUNE D'AIN-SULTAN, JJCI (CPA), n° 19, 1877. Pp 201-206.*

Both arguments have roots in repealed legal texts. For instance, the 1971 Agrarian Revolution Charter⁶⁵ stated: "first, it is necessary to put an end to the complex and diverse legal bases, by establishing a modern legal framework for private land ownership through a census of individually owned land. This would eliminate all *de facto* and *de jure* irregularities within the framework of the agrarian revolution, with the goal of achieving a unified model of private ownership", this objective became even clearer in a subsequent decree which stipulated the replacement of ownership certificates with land registry books, describing them as: the new and exclusive starting point for establishing evidence of real property ownership"⁶⁶.

This is an implicit and acceptable legal foundation, provided that it does not conflict with established legal rules and principles—most importantly, the principle of hierarchy of laws. According to this universal principle, the higher-ranking law prevails, and the lower-ranking one is excluded, his principle is also recognized in rulings by the Algerian Supreme Court. One decision states: "in the event of a conflict between a higher-ranking and a lower-ranking law, the higher-ranking law shall apply."⁶⁷, in accordance with the hierarchy of laws in Algeria, statutory law (*loi*) ranks above decrees (*décrets*), therefore, Article 827 of the Civil Code, which provides for acquisitive prescription, takes precedence over Articles 32 and 33 of Decree No. 73-32 concerning the proof of private property rights, and thus the decree articles are excluded.

The issue of hierarchy was mentioned in an old ruling by the Supreme Court in 1964, which stated that evidence in Islamic Sharia is subject to specific rules of preference (hierarchy)⁶⁸. This principle can be extended to encompass all legal rules. Similarly, some French judges relied on the same principle to reject acquisitive prescription, arguing that the title deed is superior according to the hierarchical principle of proving ownership⁶⁹. However, the French Court of Cassation rejected this approach, annulled the decision, and referred the parties back to the Grenoble Court to reconsider the case by examining the fulfillment of the conditions of acquisitive prescription and the correct application of the law⁷⁰.

This justification is also criticized for its lack of seriousness, as the unification of judicial interpretation can be achieved through other means, primarily legislative intervention. This can be done by explicitly stating that acquisitive prescription does not apply to properties governed by the land registration system. Tunisia adopted this approach in Article 50 of the Law on Real Right⁷¹s, which states: "Time limitation does not apply to registered rights, and no one may claim possession regardless of its duration." Similarly, the Omani legislator followed this path in Article 931 of the Civil Transactions Law, which begins with: "Whoever

⁶⁵ Agrarian Revolution Charter, OJ No. 97 of 1971 (repealed in 1990).

⁶⁶ Articles 32 and 33, Decree No. 73-32 of January 5, 1973, concerning the proof of private property rights, Official Journal No. 15 of 1973.

⁶⁷ SCA, REC, No: 264463, 09/10/2002, SCJ, No: 02, 2002, P 232-236.

⁶⁸ SCA (Chambre de Droit Privé), 23 décembre 1964, Daghour C/Baouchi, RASJP, v 02, n 02, 1965, , pp87-88

⁶⁹ hiérarchie des preuves de propriété.

⁷⁰ French Court of Cassation, Chambre civile 3, du 4 décembre 1991, 89-14.921, Publié au bulletin <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/juri/id/JURITEXT000007027763>, 08/08/2024

⁷¹ Law No. 05 of 1965, dated February 12, 1965, concerning the promulgation of the Code of Real Rights, published in the Official journal of Tunisia, No. 10, dated February 19 and 23, 1965, as amended and supplemented

possesses an unregistered property..., "72 implying that prescription applies only to unregistered properties. By contrast, long possession (prescription) leading to ownership is excluded for registered properties. This same approach was adopted by the Moroccan legislator, who affirmed the purifying effect of land registration in Article 261/05 of the Real Rights Code, stating: "Registered properties cannot be acquired through possession,"73 and reinforced this in Article 63 of the Real Estate Registration Law: "Prescription does not confer any real right over registered property against the registered owner, nor does it extinguish any registered real right in the land record"74.

A unified approach could also have been achieved through judicial precedent by convening all chambers of the Supreme Court to adopt a single binding opinion for all lower courts, The organic law75 regulating the Supreme Court, as well as its internal regulations76, set out the required procedures. The Supreme Court issues its decisions from one of its individual chambers, from a joint chamber, or from all chambers sitting together.

Referral is made to a joint chamber, which is composed of at least two chambers and requires a quorum of at least 15 judges, when a legal question has been or may be met with conflicting solutions in two or more chambers. If they cannot reach agreement, the president of the joint chamber notifies the First President of the Supreme Court, referring the case to all chambers77 sitting together. In addition to the above scenario, this full bench is also required when a decision under consideration would change existing jurisprudence.

The full bench is chaired by the First President of the Supreme Court and includes their deputy, the presidents of the chambers, the heads of departments, the deans of counselors in each chamber, and the reporting counselor. Decisions require the presence of at least half of the members and are adopted by a majority vote. In case of a tie, the First President's vote is decisive.

04. The Ethical Criterion:

Some supporters of the conclusive evidentiary power of the land registry argue that acquisitive prescription (adverse possession) is an unethical concept, as it constitutes a legal

⁷² "In a comparable formulation, we find Article 1158 of the Iraqi Civil Code and Article 1317 of the UAE Transactions Law."

⁷³ Law No. 08-39 on the Code of Real Rights, implemented by Royal Decree No. 1.11.178 dated November 22, 2011, published in the Official journal No. 5998 on November 24, 2011.

⁷⁴ The Royal Decree issued on August 12, 1913, concerning land registration (real estate registration), as amended and supplemented by Law No. 14-07, implemented by Royal Decree No. 1.11.177 of November 22, 2011, published in the Official journal No. 5998 on November 24, 2011.

⁷⁵ Articles 15–19 of Organic Law No. 11-12, dated June 26, 2011, organizing the Supreme Court's structure, functioning, and jurisdiction, as published in OJ No. 42 of 2011.

⁷⁶ Articles 57–64 of the Internal Rules of the Supreme Court, approved by the General Assembly on November 24, 2013, OJ No. 34 of 2014.

⁷⁷ The parties to the dispute cannot request the convening of the chambers *en banc*. See, in this regard, two Supreme Court decisions from its Commercial Chamber: Case No. 309301, decision dated 15/07/2003, *Judicial Journal*, Issue No. 01, 2003, pp. 293–297; and Case No. 350925, decision dated 11/05/2005, pp. 219–222.

theft of others' property and rights. However, this argument is rejected for the following reasons:

The "ethical framing" of the law to exclude acquisitive prescription is a selective argument, because the Algerian legal system contains a number of unjust ideas and provisions that should be studied collectively and rejected altogether for example, the annulment of contracts arising from exploitation expires after only one year⁷⁸, which is actually a very short period compared to the 15 years required for acquisitive prescription. Similarly, usury is practiced by banks in Algeria despite being unethical and religiously forbidden, so focusing exclusively on acquisitive prescription without considering these other ideas is a biased and unacceptable approach.

Morality is a relative matter; the registered owner views the acquisition by prescription as an unjust theft of their property, while society, which benefits from acquisitive prescription, sees the neglect of ownership as selfishness and abuse. Both perspectives are based on ethical grounds that should not be ignored⁷⁹, This makes acquisitive prescription a moral concept aimed at achieving a specific purpose—combating the owner's selfishness—rather than a mere arbitrary idea within the Algerian legal system., moreover, an owner who gains property through acquisitive prescription can lose it in the same way, making this principle general and abstract, applicable to everyone except for cases explicitly excluded by law (such as state property). For this reason, the Egyptian Court of Cassation holds that: "It is established in its rulings that a claimant of ownership may base their claim on any cause they deem establishing ownership. Acquisition of ownership through long prescription is an independent cause of ownership, which in itself legitimizes possession and excludes the characterization of usurpation"⁸⁰, this also means that the law permits actions sufficient (legally) to remove criminal liability.

It is necessary to distinguish between what ethics require before legal institutions take action and what comes afterward⁸¹; since the legislator's adoption of a particular approach also morally obliges us to implement it. The judge is ethically tasked with adhering to the true interpretation of the legal text as its custodian. Moreover, the flaw of the ethical rule is that it lacks binding force—it is nothing but a shadow hovering at the edges of the legal rule⁸², waiting to be adopted to become binding. Until then, this argument does not even deserve the effort of a response.

The main argument against the ethical standard is that its proponents are contradictory: on one hand, they seek to unify the evidence of real estate ownership, while on the other hand, they resort to using multiple sources of law (ethics and legislation), More than that, they apply

⁷⁸ Article 90 of the Civil Code.

⁷⁹ Every idea carries with it an underlying set of ethics; see: Mark Greenberg, *The Moral Impact Theory of Law*, 123 *Yale L.J.* 1288, 1302 (2014).

⁸⁰ The Egyptian Court of Cassation, Civil Seventh Circuit (B), Decision No. 4929 of Judicial Year 85, session dated 20/06/2021.

⁸¹ Mark Greenberg, *id.*, p 1337.

⁸² Ripert had already anticipated the emergence of these hybrid forms whose vicissitudes he described: "[...] when the moral rule fails to take on a legal form, we sometimes see it wandering at the borders of law, requesting at least to be considered in the faded form of a natural obligation, and this is no less a curious aspect of legal life than these ghosts of non-binding obligations, which overly logical minds find difficult to accept." see : Dominique Terre, *Droit, Morale et Sociologie*, 54 *L'Année Sociologique* 486, 499 (2004).

ethics and exclude legislation, even though legislation should take precedence according to the hierarchy of sources outlined in Article 1 of the Algerian Civil Code.

05/ Criterion of the Specificity of Property Rights:

One of the most prominent characteristics of ownership is its permanence, therefore, acquisitive prescription cannot be accepted because it threatens ownership, This argument is logically very strong, although the permanence of ownership cannot be fully accepted logically, as it is based on relative sources, and relativity usually does not lead to an absolute right, this idea is echoed in Tunisian jurisprudence, which states: "Prescription in itself, while it may confer ownership, can also interrupt it, and the defendant has the right to invoke the interrupting prescription to dismiss the claim."⁸³ It concludes that a claim to ownership is barred by acquisitive prescription. This was confirmed in another ruling stating: "Merely relying on acquisitive possession is sufficient to override any argument related to prior entitlement at the beginning of the possession period, considering that possession is a conclusive legal presumption."⁸⁴ This is further supported by another decision rejecting an appeal court's stance that ownership is proven solely by the deed without connection to possession, reasoning that the opposing party did not challenge the opponent with acquisitive possession of ownership⁸⁵. Another ruling states: "Where the ownership claim is based on the deed, the ownership right remains valid in favor of the buyer unless this right is extinguished by acquisition through prescription by another"⁸⁶, this can be represented mathematically as follows:

"From a mathematical perspective, this means that at the initial moment in time ($t = 0$), the registered owner possessed all the rights and powers of ownership, while the possessor held none. However, at a later moment ($t = 15$)—that is, after 15 years (or any other period depending on the specific case and the country)—the owner is stripped of their rights, and the possessor transforms into the new legal owner. Mathematically, the matter is very straightforward: it is simply the transformation of the possessor into the owner (acquisitive prescription). It is the moment when diligent effort is rewarded."

6. The Criterion of Differentiating Between the Pure Torrens System and the Algerian Torrens System:

This is a hypothetical argument that has not been explicitly stated,⁸⁷ but it is worth discussing because the issue is purely academic and requires us to gather the most important arguments and examine them to approach the truth, the essence of this criterion is that the Torrens system is a real property registration system, and since Algeria has adopted it, it is assumed that we must always defend this system and its principles, accordingly, one might

⁸³ TCC, Civil Cassation Decision No: 7534, 09/02/1971.

⁸⁴ TCC, Civil Cassation Decision No: 1245, 10/04/1979.

⁸⁵ TCC, Civil Cassation Decision No: 30880, 22/02/1994.

⁸⁶ TCC, Civil Cassation Decision No: 25904, 1992/01/14 and Civil Cassation Decision No. 4626, .2000/12/14

⁸⁷ This was stated in an American article, which noted that the flaws do not lie in the Torrens system itself, but rather in how it has been implemented and in the functioning of the administration. Therefore, the focus should be on improving the system's operation, not on circumventing it. See: James R. Carret and Land Transfer, a reply to criticisms of the Torrens system, 7 Harv. L. Rev. 24, 24–31 (1893).

argue that the land title (land book) should have precedence over acquisitive prescription to ensure legal security; however, this approach is rejected, because the system has become a source of legal disputes rather than a solution, notably, the state does not bear any liability for errors committed in this domain, instead leaving the parties to bear all the costs (lawyer, bailiff, expert fees, etc.). There is no compensation fund in place, therefore, the outcomes of the cadastral survey, which has proven to be flawed, should not be favored⁸⁸.

IV. Third: Personal Position

The fact that both the land register and acquisitive prescription are based on a legal foundation that justifies them leads us to borrow the description given by the High Court of Australia, which is that the matter represents a competition between equitable interests⁸⁹ that must be weighed and balanced. I believe that the solution lies either in invoking legislative liability or in challenging the constitutionality of Article 827 of the Civil Code.

01/ Legislative Liability:

Historically rooted in Ancient Greece, any citizen could challenge a law ratified by the National Assembly (Ekklesia) if it contained serious defects or contradicted existing laws, with penalties ranging from fines to the execution of the law's author⁹⁰. However, this concept of legislative liability was later abandoned, and the prevailing general rule became that legislators bear no responsibility for the exercise of their legislative powers⁹¹. This immunity is justified by several factors, most notably that legislation falls within the domain of political activity, which is shielded from judicial oversight due to the legislature's sovereign authority to enact laws in the name of the people. Moreover, recognizing such liability is seen as theoretically and legally impossible⁹²: theoretically, the state treasury cannot bear the burden of compensating all individuals harmed by laws, and legally, it would violate the principle of separation of powers by allowing the judiciary to interfere with legislative functions. Legislative acts are also considered discretionary, meaning the legislator is free to legislate or abstain, provided that the constitutionally prescribed procedures are followed—once they are, there is no legal basis for liability.

⁸⁸ *It may also be appropriate here to present a personal argument: in our rural area, my maternal grandfather owns more than 10 hectares, but according to the cadastral survey, he is recorded as owning only 3.5 hectares. Similarly, my paternal grandfather owns 4.5 hectares, yet the survey shows only 2 hectares in his name, there are many other such examples.*

⁸⁹ *High Court of Australia, Latec Investments Ltd v Hotel Terrigal Pty Ltd, 1965HCA 17, and Heid v Reliance Finance Corporation Pty Ltd see [:https://eresources.hcourt.gov.au/showbyHandle/1/10804](https://eresources.hcourt.gov.au/showbyHandle/1/10804) and <https://eresources.hcourt.gov.au/showbyHandle/1/11588>*

⁹⁰ *Bronislav Totskyi, Legal Certainty as a Basic Principle of the Land Law of Ukraine, 21 J. Juris. 204, 206 (2014) and Virgilio Zapatero Gómez, Language and Rule of Law in Classical Athens, 5 Stud. Theory & Prac. Legis. 3, 19 (2019).*

⁹¹ *Olivier Gohin, La responsabilité de l'État en tant que législateur, 50 Rev. Int'l D. Comp. 595, 596 (1998).*

⁹² *Jean-F. Brunet, De la responsabilité de l'État législateur (Doctoral thesis, Univ. of Paris, 1936), at 24–30.*

However, accepting this claim in absolute terms risks opening the door to legislative abuse, which may even reach the level of legal corruption, so long as the legislator is not held accountable for how they exercise their legislative function. This has led some legal scholars to characterize such immunity as a denial of justice, as it runs counter to the spirit of the rule of law. Consequently, efforts have been made to establish foundations for legislative liability⁹³. Initially, this responsibility was grounded in the concept of fault; however, this proved inadequate due to the judiciary's lack of jurisdiction to assess errors made by the legislative authority. A second theory, proposed by the jurist Hauriou, suggested that the basis for liability lay in the concept of unjust enrichment. Yet, this idea was criticized as unrealistic and lacking sound logic. Jurist Duguit later introduced a new foundation based on harm to a private interest that the legislator failed to consider. Due to the limitations of these earlier views, a more coherent approach emerged, resting on the notion of "social risk"⁹⁴. This concept links liability to damages resulting from the disruption of the economic balance of those addressed by the legal rule, requiring compensation through a designated fund, which would be incorporated into the economic impact of the law and distributed according to the principle of equality in bearing public burdens⁹⁵.

The French Council of State contributed to establishing the concept and clarifying its conditions, which are derived from the collection of rulings it issued in this field⁹⁶. Among the most important conditions are that the law must not have overlooked compensation, and the injured party must prove that the legislator intended for the concerned person to bear a burden that does not ordinarily fall upon them. Furthermore⁹⁷, a ruling declaring the law unconstitutional is required, which is a complex condition that cannot always be fulfilled. Additionally, the claim must be filed within four years from the date the damage occurred.

Legislative liability is a fundamental link between legal security and real estate legislation. Therefore, this liability can be applied to the conflict previously outlined between acquisitive prescription and registered rights. It must be acknowledged that whether acquisitive prescription or registered rights are given priority, a definite harm will befall the losing party, affecting their financial standing by denying them ownership rights through an implicit confiscation.

⁹³ Gohin Olivier, *id*, p 596.

⁹⁴ Maurice Nakhla, *Liability of Public Authority (in Arabic)*, 1st ed., Legal Publications House, n.p., n.d., p. 132.

⁹⁵ Jean-F. Brunet, *id*, p 71, 82.

⁹⁶ French Council of State, *décisions* n° 425981: <https://www.conseil-etat.fr/fr/arianeweb/CE/decision/2019-12-24/425981>, et n° 425983 <https://www.conseil-etat.fr/fr/arianeweb/CE/decision/2019-12-24/425983>, et n° 428162 <https://www.conseil-etat.fr/fr/arianeweb/CE/decision/2019-12-24/428162>.

⁹⁷ "that nothing, neither in the text of the law itself nor in its preparatory works, nor in the entire circumstances of the case, allows one to think that the legislator intended to make the concerned party bear a burden that does not normally fall upon them." CEF, *décision de société "La Fleurette"*, N° 51704 de 14 janvier 1938, consulté: 08/08/2022, site: <https://www.conseil-etat.fr/fr/arianeweb/CE/decision/1938-01-14/51704>.

Referring back to the relevant laws, ownership is a comprehensive and exclusive right characterized by permanence, and it cannot be confiscated except for the public interest and against fair and equitable compensation, which is not achieved in this case. Prioritizing acquisitive prescription would cause legislative harm to the registered rights holder because the law favoring prescription damages their legal status as owner. Conversely, prioritizing the registered rights holder would harm the person who meets the conditions of possession, due to the exclusion of their status as owner despite meeting the legal requirements, this situation necessitates invoking legislative liability, as the legislator has not fully discharged their duty in organizing the conflicting legal interests.

02/ Challenging the Constitutionality of Article 827 of the Algerian Civil Code:

Here, we face only two options: the first is to rule that the article is constitutional, which would then confirm and uphold all the arguments mentioned above and the second is to rule that it is unconstitutional, which would resolve the current legal conflict, therefore, the challenge to the constitutionality⁹⁸ must be based on the following points:

First Reason / Violation of the Values of Justice and Solidarity (Preamble of the Constitution):

The preamble states, "The people fortified by their deep-rooted spiritual values, and preserving their traditions of solidarity and justice", since the preamble is an integral part of the constitution, these values must be respected by the legislator and cannot be ignored or neglected during legislation.

Second Reason / Violation of Articles 02 and 11/03 of the Constitution:

Because acquisitive prescription contradicts Islamic law, especially since ownership is based on lawful possession. This means that an owner who cannot justify the reason for their possession does not benefit from it, and the holder of the legitimate document takes precedence.

Third Reason / Violation of Articles 16 and 60 of the Constitution:

These articles require institutions to guarantee rights in general, and property rights in particular, as well as prohibit expropriation except with fair and equitable compensation. Such compensation is absent in acquisitive prescription, which effectively confiscates ownership without compensation.

Fourth Reason / Violation of Article 37 of the Constitution:

Which guarantees equality of all citizens and prohibits discrimination among them. Acquisitive prescription creates inequality and discrimination against owners with legitimate title deeds, since acquisitive prescription can be proven by any means, while ownership backed by title deeds is proven only by the deed itself.

⁹⁸ This matter is governed by Organic Law No: 22-19 in 25/07/2022, which sets out the procedures and methods for notification and referral before the Constitutional Court (OJ No: 51 of 2022).

Fifth Reason: Violation of Article 34 of the Constitution:

Constitutional provisions related to fundamental rights are binding on all authorities and bodies, and they must not be subjected to restrictions that undermine their essence. Article 827 of the Civil Code constitutes a serious violation of the core of the right to property, as it effectively destroys it and removes it from the owner's control.

Furthermore, the constitutional legislator has imposed on the ordinary legislator, when enacting laws concerning rights and freedoms, that such laws must be clear and stable. However, following the interpretations by the Supreme Court and lower courts reveals significant discrepancies regarding the application of this article, as highlighted in the aforementioned rulings. This undermines its clarity and subjects it to subjective interpretations far from objective standards, hindering intellectual (not just physical) access to the text.

Therefore, the fate of a fundamental legal right (property), which is among the highest rights, cannot be left to the discretion of judges' varying interpretations. This situation leaves litigants confused as to which interpretation will be applied, resulting in a breach of judicial security, which is the living application of the principle of legal certainty.

Sixth Reason: Violation of Article 27/02 of the Constitution:

The 1971 Agricultural Revolution Charter states: "It is necessary first to put an end to the complex and diverse legal foundations by striving to establish private land ownership based on a modern legal framework, through the inventory of lands owned by individuals. This allows for the elimination of all factual and legal situations within the scope of the Agricultural Revolution, aiming to achieve a unified model of private ownership."

In line with this objective, Law 75/74 was enacted to purify real estate ownership. Therefore, the application of acquisitive prescription in surveyed areas, and on properties with registered ownership titles, constitutes a legal retrogression to the period before 1975, disregarding the work of the surveying institutions in Algeria.

V. Conclusion:

The Algerian real estate system is experiencing a crisis of legal proof, as evidenced by the contradictions in Supreme Court rulings regarding the prioritization between acquisitive prescription as a means of acquiring property rights and the land register (land title) as a result of the cadastral survey system. This contradiction contributes to the violation of legal security, which has been enshrined as a constitutional principle since 2020, due to this legal inconsistency, resorting to the judiciary to protect property rights has become a gamble, often resulting in the loss of property for those holding official titles—depending solely on the judge's personal view. Judges may align with either the doctrine of acquisitive prescription or that of land registration, making litigation outcomes highly uncertain.

Therefore, we propose that lawyers raise a constitutional objection against Article 827 of the Civil Code, which permits acquisitive prescription on all private properties. This article was introduced in 1975, during a time when official title documents were scarce—conditions

that no longer exist. Accordingly, the jurisprudential principle that "laws expire when the reasons for their existence disappear" should apply, filing this constitutional challenge would resolve the inconsistency once and for all—either by declaring Article 827 constitutional or unconstitutional. This decision would be binding on all state institutions in accordance with Article 198(5) of the Constitution, additionally, we suggest that the Supreme Court ethically commit to a unified legal opinion on similar disputes, in line with its role in standardizing judicial interpretation as required by Article 179(3) of the Constitution, ultimately, as a comprehensive solution, the legislator must reformulate Article 827 in a clear and precise manner that guarantees both legal and judicial certainty for owners and possessors